

Work Environment on Job Satisfaction with mediating effect of Motivation among School Teachers in Lahore, Pakistan

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Abstract—This study was aimed to assess the relationship between work environment, motivation and job satisfaction in private school teachers of Lahore, Pakistan. Standardized questionnaires were used to collect the data from 300 private school's teachers. The data was analyzed through SPSS by using correlation, principle component analysis and multiple regression. The results indicates that there is a positive relationship between work environment and job satisfaction in school teachers. Result showed that there is a significantly positive impact of Work Environment on Motivation and there is also a positive influence of Motivation¹ on Job Satisfaction. Results indicate that Motivation partially mediates between Work Environment and Job Satisfaction of school teachers in Lahore, Pakistan.

Keywords— Education Sector, Job satisfaction, Motivation, Teacher, Work environment.

I. INTRODUCTION

The present study aims to explore the relationship of job satisfaction, work environment and motivation among school teachers and also mediating effect of motivation on work environment and job satisfaction. There is an increasing demand for services from the consumers and fast paced changes in global competition so it is essential for any organization to make improvements in order to survive (Klijn&Tomic, 2009) [1]. As organizations with committed employees achieve better long-term performance, companies try to develop a team of satisfied employees (Luchak&Gellatly, 2007) [2].

Job satisfaction is an approach of workers about their work. Job satisfaction is about holding the right person to the right job keeping them satisfied as it plays a crucial role in keeping the employees within the institution.[3]

Work environment comprises of social, cultural, organizational and environmental elements. Social elements include working relationship, interaction and

association with colleagues. A person's beliefs, attitude, values, and religious components are part of cultural element. The size and structure of the workplace, employee-employer relationships, management abilities, leaderships, delegation and all such things are organizational elements which affect job satisfaction. Financial, social, technical and governmental or political influences constitute environmental elements (Abou, 2013)[3].

Motivation is a wish or readiness to do something or act in a certain way. Motivation is the result of different factors such as strength of the need or reward value of the goal and expectations of the employee. Motivation is the important factor to motive the employees towards the success of the institute (Akhtar & Aziz, 2014)[4].

Chandrasekar (2011) argued that managing abilities, time and drive, all are needed for improving the overall performance of the organization however human interactions and relations are more significant in job satisfaction as compared to money[5].

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Work motivation initiates work-related behavior, and controls its form, course, intensity, and length (Pinder, 1998)[6]. According to Luthans (1998) a process that causes, boosts, guides, and maintains behavior and performance is known as motivation[7].

Baah and Amoako (2011) described that the motivational factors such as the nature of work, the sense of achievement, acknowledgment, work responsibility, and opportunities for personal growth etc helps employees to find their worth and value. This can increase their level of motivation which will enhance internal happiness of employees and as a result will cause satisfaction [8].

Motivation is the main factor that has an effect on the job satisfaction of employees. According to Ali and Ahmed (2009) there is a significant relationship between motivation and job satisfaction. Rewards are directly

related with the motivation and job satisfaction of the employees. A positive change in work motivation can be brought by variations in rewards which lead to job satisfaction [9].

Job satisfaction may be affected by different factors within the working environment such as salary, working hours, independence given to employees, structure of organization and relationship between employees & administration (Lane, Esser, Holte, & Anne, 2010) [10].

Horwitz et al (2003) proposed that inspiring work environment and backing of the top management can motivate the workers [11]. Bakotic and Babic (2013) argued that working condition is an important factor for job satisfaction, so workers under difficult working conditions are dissatisfied. Hence, it is essential for the management to improve the working conditions to increase overall performance [12].

Job satisfaction according to Spector (1997) is the degree to which people like (satisfaction) or dislike (dissatisfaction) their work [13]. Sell and Cleal (2011) stated that job satisfaction is directly affected by different psychosocial and work environment factors like work place, social support and that increase in rewards does not improve the employees' dissatisfaction level [14].

According to Balzar et al. (1997) job satisfaction is employees' expectation towards work and feeling about their work environment [15]. Different objectives are lead by different kinds of satisfaction and behaviors that rise from different types of motivation in rewards (Luthanset al. 2005) [16]. Rewards were expected to have impact on satisfaction of the employee (Milne, 2007) [17]. Employee who reports high job satisfaction is motivated by rewards, and rewards supported work engagement (Vandenberghe & Trembley 2008) [18]. According to Zaini's (2009) job satisfaction is linked with the monetary compensation (salary, raise, and bonus) [19] and non-monetary compensation is one of the most important factors in both private and public sectors (Furham et al. 2009) [20].

Rao (2005) discussed that job satisfaction for a person acts as a motivation to work and in addition motivation results in job satisfaction [21]. Velnampy (2008) concluded that job satisfaction boosts job participation and better performance also makes people feel more contented and dedicated to the institution [22].

III. Hypothesis

This study is concerned about the impact of work environment on job satisfaction. The purpose of this study is to find out the effect of employee's motivation on job satisfaction specifically in school teachers of Lahore, Pakistan. Firstly, it was hypothesized that job satisfaction, work environment and motivation were likely to relate with each other. Secondly, it was assumed that motivation was likely to mediate the relation between work environment and job satisfaction.

IV. Research Model

Legend:

WE= Work Environment

M= Motivation

JS= Job satisfaction

V. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study Cross sectional correlation research design and non probability purposive sampling strategy was used. Data was collected from 300 teachers working in private schools of Lahore, Pakistan.

Participants who have experience of teaching of at least six months were included. Teachers who have teaching experience of less than six months were excluded.

In addition to gathering demographic information, following three tools will be used for the collection of data.

Work Environment Survey (2007) the survey (Public Service Secretariat & Newfoundland and Labrador Statistics Agency, 2007) 10 questionnaire items were extracted, motivation was measured through Situational Motivation Scale (SIMS) SIMS (Guay et al, 2000) 5 items were extracted [23] whereas to measure Job Satisfaction, 10 items of Job Satisfaction Survey (JSS) (Spector, 1994), were extracted [24].

VI. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Factor analysis is the process of reducing data in few variables who acts as a representative of complete set of variables. Principal Component Analysis was carried out and the following tables show the results. KMO and Bartlett's test of sphericity was applied to check whether enough data is available for factor analysis.

Table I - KMO & Bartlett's Test

Constructs	Number of Items	KMO – Measur eof sample adequacy	Bartlett's Test – Sphericity Chi-square	Bartlett's Test – Sphericity Sig.
Work Environment	10	.906	5132.492	.000
Motivation	05	.728	3000.142	.000
Job Satisfaction	10	.863	2262.702	.000

If KMO value is greater than 0.6 then it is acceptable for good factor analysis, so all constructs are adequate in accordance to sample.

Table I shows the p-value of Bartlett which is smaller than 0.001 for all variables which verify null hypothesis of no correlation.

Table II - Eigenvalues & Total Variance

Constructs	Initial eigenvalues			
	Components	Total	% of variance explained	Cumulative % of variance explained
Work Environment	Comp 1	6.845	68.446	68.446
Motivation	Comp 1	3.998	79.969	79.969
Job satisfaction	Comp 1	1.615	53.847	53.847

Principal components are declared whose eigenvalue is more than 1, for all constructs eigenvalues are greater than 1.

Table III – Component Matrix

ITEMS	COMPONENT
WORK ENVIRONMENT	WE
While at work, I feel like I belong to a team.	.862
My manager or supervisor assigns work fairly.	.899
I have positive working relationship with my coworkers.	.859
I have opportunities to socialize with my co workers.	.720
It seems as a person leader care about me.	.711
I am satisfied with the quality of the supervision.	.849
I trust the senior leadership of my department.	.876
Overall, my organization treats me with respect.	.802
I am contented with my working hours.	.832
To balance my work and personal life I have support at work.	.840
MOTIVATION	M
I find this job interesting.	.892
I am doing it for my sake	.923
I find this job pleasant	.887
This activity is good for me	.896
I feel good when doing this job.	.872
JOB SATISFACTION	JS
I feel I am being paid adequately	.829
My supervisor is quite competent in work	.587
Communications seem good within this organization	.764
The benefits we receive are adequate	.884
I am satisfied with current job	.884
I like doing my work	.910

The benefit package we have is reasonable	.758
I enjoy my coworkers	.720
I feel proud of my job	.468
I am happy with my chances for promotion	.616

WE loading values are 0.899 to 0.711 > 0.40

M loading values are 0.923 to 0.872 > 0.40

JS loading values are 0.910 to 0.469 > 0.40

Table IV: Demographic characteristics of the sample (n=300)

Variables	F	%
Gender		
Male	150	50
Female	150	50
Marital Status		
Unmarried	165	55
Married	128	42.6
Divorced	5	1.6
Widow/widower	2	0.6
Education		
Graduate	50	16
Masters	165	55
M.phil	85	29
P.hd	0	0

f=frequency, %=percentage

Reliability and validity of constructs can be checked through the values of Cronbach's alpha as shown in table V. Table shows that Cronbach's alpha's values are in between 0.739 to 0.815 which possess the high reliability. Higher the values of Cronbach's alpha means more reliable and valid. This table shows that the values of Cronbach's alpha of Work Environment, Motivation and Job Satisfaction are 0.815, 0.761 and 0.739 respectively.

Table V: Reliability of Measures

Constructs	Valid N	Numbers of Items	Cronbach's alpha
Work Environment	300	10	0.815
Motivation	298	5	0.761
Job Satisfaction	299	10	0.739

Cronbach's alpha's values are in between 0.739 to 0.815 which possess the high reliability.

Table VI shows that the values of Work Environment ranges from 0.312 to 0.668, Motivation ranges from 0.286 to 0.668 and

Job Satisfaction ranges from 0.452 to 0.535 which shows all constructs are moderately correlated.

Adjusted R2	0.590
F-Statistics	979.094*

* = represents significance at less than 0.01
Value in parentheses representative t-ratios

Table VI: Correlation

Variables	Values	Status
Work Environment	0.312 – 0.668	Moderate
Motivation	0.286 – 0.668	Moderate
Job Satisfaction	0.452 – 0.535	Moderate

In order to determine the effects of independent variable (Work Environment) on mediating variable (Motivation), mediating variable (Motivation) on dependent variable (Job Satisfaction) and similarly independent variable (Work Environment) on dependent variable (Job Satisfaction) Regression analysis was used.

Figure 1: Relationship Diagram

Legend:

WE= Work Environment

M= Motivation

JS= Job satisfaction

*** = represents significant level below 0.001**

Value in parentheses representative t-ratios

Above figure shows that there is a significantly positive influence of Work environment on Motivation (= 0.636, p < 0.001). Similarly it shows there is a positive impact of Motivation on Job Satisfaction (= 0.700, p < 0.001). It also shows there is a positive relationship between Work Environment and Job Satisfaction (= 0.692, p < 0.001).

Direct effect of Independent Variable (Work Environment) on Dependent Variable (Job Satisfaction)

Table VII shows that there is positive influence of Work Environment on Job Satisfaction (= 0.692, p < 0.001).

Table VII:

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable
	Job Satisfaction
Work Environment	0.692* (35.217)

Table VIII: Multiple Regression Analysis for Mediation

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable
	Job Satisfaction
Work Environment	0.399* (17.639)
Motivation	0.452* (20.241)

Table VIII shows that Motivation partially mediates between Work Environment and Job Satisfaction (Motivation = 0.452, sig. < 0.01).

VII. CONCLUSION

Findings uncovered that there is significant positive relationship between motivation and teacher job satisfaction. Thus, factually statistical positive relationship is likewise found between work environment and teacher/instructor job satisfaction. Nonetheless, it is found that teacher’s job satisfaction in to a great extent brought on by motivational variables.

XIII. LIMITATIONS/ IMPLICATIONS

Sample size is small. Results cannot be generalize for whole population. Extraneous variables duration of jobs and work experience should be controlled.

This is a critical examination effort with respect to the impact of workplace and motivational variables on teacher job satisfaction in private sector schools of Pakistan and it has practical suggestions for schools can create a work environment that may enhance employee motivation and job satisfaction which might help the organization by increasing productivity and profit. This study will likewise give a decent establishment to future exploration on related subjects.

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